

Synthesis and Structure Elucidation of Some Dibutyltin (IV) Phenoxides

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Reactions of dibutyltin oxide with certain phenols in molar ratio 1 : 1 yield two types of compounds with the general formula (a) $[\text{OAr}]_2\text{Bu}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{O}$ and (b) $(\text{OAR})\text{Bu}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OH})$. In type (a) compounds ArOH is phenol, β -naphthol, *o*- and *p*-chlorophenol, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresol, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenol, *p*-aminophenol and *p*-cyanophenol. These are dimeric in non-coordinating solvents at room temperature and contain two types of tin atoms—one in tetrahedral and the other in pentacoordinated state. The type (b) compounds are formed with phenols such as 2, 4, 6-trinitrophenol, 2, 4, 6-tribromophenol, 2, 6-dibromo-4-chlorophenol, 8-hydroxyquinoline. These are monomers in solution, however, polymerisation occurs through hydroxyl groups in solid state. Besides, two phenols, 8-hydroxyquinoline and *o*-hydroxypyridine yield compounds of the general formula $\text{Bu}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OAr})_2$ in which the two butyl groups are *cis* to each other. All these compounds have been characterised with the help of molecular weight determination freezing point depression method in benzene and by Rast method in camphor, infrared, and ^1H NMR spectra.

THE reaction of diorganotin oxide with many compounds containing active hydrogen e.g. carboxylic acids, alcohols, mercaptans and amines have been studied by many workers¹⁻¹⁰. In the case of phenols the formation of diorganotin diphenoxides has been reported according to the reaction (a)

However, no data have been given in support of this claim.

Considine and his coworkers¹⁰ while studying the reaction of dibutyltin oxides with phenols in toluene observed that the amount of water isolated azeotropically was never equal to that predicted by reaction (a). Besides the starting phenol was recovered which suggests that the reaction may be proceeding according to equation (b)

The compounds of the type II have already been reported in many patents^{4,7,8}. However, Mehrotra et al.⁹ have reported product (III) in case of *o*-aminophenol.

In the present investigations reactions of dibutyltin oxide and phenols in molar ratio one to one and one to two have been studied. The structures of the products obtained in these reactions have been investigated with the help of molecular weight determination by Rast as well as cryoscopic method, infrared ($4000\text{-}200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and ^1H NMR spectra.

Experimental

Reactions of equimolar quantities of Bu_2SnO and phenols were carried out in benzene, CH_2Cl_2 , toluene cyclohexane, benzene/alcohol mixture. After 5-10 min refluxing Bu_2SnO went into solution completely. The reaction mixture was further refluxed for 15 minutes and the slightly turbid solution was filtered. The solvent was removed by distillation. The last traces of solvent were removed by vacuum. The solids obtained thus were crystallised from petroleum ether $60^\circ\text{-}80^\circ$ or benzene. Physical data on the compounds prepared during these investigations are given in Tables 1-6. For comparison, spectral data for aryl methyl ethers has also been included. Ethers were obtained by the action of dimethyl sulphate on phenols in alkaline medium and purity of products was checked by usual methods.

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra ($4600\text{-}650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on a Specord 71 IR Spectrophotometer. Far I.R. spectra ($650\text{-}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were obtained through the courtesy of Sophisticated Instrumental Laboratory, I.I.T. Madras. Proton NMR was taken on a Tesla Bs-487C 80 MHz instrument. Carbon and hydrogen were analysed by the Australian Microanalytical Service, Melbourne. Tin was estimated as tin dioxide.

Results and Discussion

During the reactions of dibutyltin oxide with certain phenols in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio the products fall into three categories, A, B and C.

Category A

In category A the compounds of dibutyltin oxide with phenol, β -naphthol, *o*-chlorophenol, *p*-chloro-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA [CALCULATED VALUES IN PARENTHESES]

Sr. No.	Compound of Bu ₂ SnO with	Formula	M.P. °C	Sn (%)	C (%)	H (%)	M.W. by Rast method in camphor	M.W. by freezing point depression method in benzene	Solubility
1.	Phenol	C ₂₈ H ₄₆ O ₃ Sn ₂	137.39	35.48 (35.42)	49.60 (50.42)	6.88 (6.90)	642 (666)	1328 (1332)	CCl ₄ , CHCl ₃ , C ₆ H ₆
2.	β-Naphthol	C ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₃ Sn ₂	96-97	31.61 (30.8)	56.21 (56.42)	6.54 (6.26)	720 (766)	1500 (1532)	"
3.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ Cl ₂ O ₃ Sn ₂	103	31.50 (32.10)	41.14 (45.71)	6.4 (6.0)	700 (735)	1469 (1470)	"
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	"	125	32.70 (32.10)	45.57 (45.71)	6.43 (6.0)	714 (735)	1438 (1470)	"
5.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ N ₂ O ₇ Sn ₂	248	31.65 (31.22)	44.25 (44.44)	5.78 (5.82)	728 (756)	1498 (1512)	"
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ N ₂ O ₇ Sn ₂	126	31.0 (31.22)	44.47 (44.44)	5.96 (5.82)	729 (756)	1480 (1512)	"
7.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenol	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ O ₃ Sn ₂	105	32.8 (34.0)	50.61 (51.8)	7.46 (7.45)	667 (695)	1420 (1390)	"
8.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenol	"	thick liquid	33.2 (34.0)	—	—	707 (695)	1387 (1390)	"
9.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenol	"	thick liquid	33.3 (34.0)	50.84 (51.8)	7.26 (7.45)	638 (695)	1427 (1390)	"
10.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₃ Sn ₂	144	33.1 (33.9)	47.61 (48.26)	6.73 (6.9)	670 (696)	—	Forms fine suspension in benzene.
11.	<i>p</i> -Cyanophenol	C ₃₀ H ₄₄ N ₂ O ₃ Sn ₂	230	32.1 (33.05)	—	—	761 (716)	—	Slightly soluble in benzene.
12.	2,4,6-tribromophenol	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ Br ₃ O ₂ Sn	80	20.3 (20.3)	—	—	594 (579)	560 (579)	CCl ₄ , CHCl ₃ , C ₆ H ₆ .
13.	2,4,6-Trinitrophenol	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₈ Sn	162	25.0 (24.74)	36.0 (35.2)	4.63 (4.4)	decomposes	—	Insoluble in benzene.
14.	2,6-Dibromo-4-chlorophenol	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ Br ₂ ClO ₂ Sn	80	22.0 (20.15)	—	—	515 (534)	535 (534)	Benzene
15.	8-Hydroxypyridine (1 : 1)	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ NO ₂ Sn	260	30.33 (30.02)	—	—	415 (393)	—	Insoluble in benzene
16.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxypyridine (2 : 1)	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Sn	105	27.0 (28.0)	—	—	435 (420)	—	"
17.	8-Hydroxyquinoline (2 : 1)	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ Sn	155	23.0 (22.89)	59.24 (60.01)	5.8 (5.8)	528 (520)	—	"

phenol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol, *p*-cresol, *p*-nitrophenol, *m*-nitrophenol, *p*-aminophenol, *p*-cyanophenol have been found to possess the general formula [(OAr)Bu₂Sn]₂O.

Infrared spectra

The absence of any band round 3200-300 cm⁻¹ and the appearance of a strong medium-broad band at 2900 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) shows the complete elimination of phenolic proton by Bu₂Sn(IV) moiety. The Ar(C=C) stretching frequencies fall by 10-30 cm⁻¹ on compound formation as compared to the corresponding anisoles. This indicates the better electron withdrawing nature of Bu₂Sn(IV) than the methyl group perhaps due to greater effective nuclear charge of tin. This also raises the ν_{as}(C-O) slightly (5-25 cm⁻¹). The bands in the region 500 to 600 cm⁻¹ (Table 3) have been ascribed to Sn-C and Sn-OR stretches. The ν_{as}(Sn-O-Sn) has been observed at 854 cm⁻¹ in case of [Bis(*o*-diphenylarsinobenzoato) dibutyltin] oxide¹². However, Mehrotra et al⁹ attribute bands in this region to the presence of

the form of Sn Sn ring. In the present investigations,

each compound been found to possess a band in 870-825 cm⁻¹ region which has been assigned to asymmetric stretch of distannoxane bond present in

the form of Sn Sn ring. The band around

600 cm⁻¹ has been ascribed to symmetric stretch of (Sn-O-Sn) bond¹³. A weak band at 425 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to bending mode of (Sn-O-Sn) bond. The weak intensity of δ(Sn-O-Sn) may be ascribed to a tendency to linearity of Sn-O-Sn system. The presence of a strong band at 300 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to Sn←O bond in the compounds under study^{14,15}.

All the above bands, however, have an upward shift when an electronegative group is attached to benzene ring at *o*- or *p*-position. Greater electronegativity of the phenoxide achieved by the attachment of electronegative groups to it increases the ionic character of Sn-O-Ph bond thereby increasing the effective nuclear charge on tin and the stretching frequencies of Sn-C, Sn-O and Sn-O-Sn bands go up. In case of tetrabutyl di-*p*-nitrophenoxy distannoxane the ν_{as}(C-O) occurs at 50 cm⁻¹ higher than that in case of tetrabutyl diphenoxy distannoxane. This has also been attributed to the greater covalent character

of Sn-O bond in the latter case. Since, there is almost no change in the stretching frequencies of nitro, cyano and amino groups in case of *p*-nitro-, *p*-cyano and *p*-amino phenols respectively, the possibility of their participation in coordination to tin in solution is ruled out.

¹HNMR

The position of phenyl protons and in particular of ortho ring protons in ¹HNMR spectrum shift upfield by 10-20 cps (Table 4) for the compounds under investigations when compared with those of respective anisoles (aryl methyl ethers). The upfield shift of ring protons may be attributed to (i) decreased paramagnetic shielding as a result of decreased ring currents due to electron withdrawing nature of tin moiety and (ii) diamagnetic anisotropic effect, which is greater at ortho positions.

In the present investigations, the centre of complex multiplets due to butyl groups has been found at $\sigma \approx 1.2$ ppm. A perusal of Table 4, however, shows that there is little effect of substituents on the position of butyl protons excluding their direct interaction with tin.

In view of above the following two structures are possible :

However, the eight membered ring structure V may be eliminated on the basis of following points.

(i) It suggests a polymeric structure while the molecular weights found cryoscopically correspond to a dimer.

(ii) Structure V shows the coordination of

phenoxy group to tin. In the presence of coordinating substance DMSO-d₆, the proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum due to phenoxy protons does not change except due to solvent effects.

The structure VI has been established with the help of x-ray diffraction by Okawara¹⁶ for R=Me and x=OSi(CH₃)₃. In the above structure, the

four membered ring Sn-O-Sn-O has been assigned

a skeletal vibration at 400 cm⁻¹¹⁷. In all the compounds a band around 400 cm⁻¹ has been observed. This indicates a similar structure for these compounds.

The molecular weight determinations in benzene correspond to the dimer visualised in structure IV. This explains the breakage of dimer in Rast method as well as the long range in their melting points.

Category B

A perusal of Table 5 for compounds of Bu₂SnO (IV) with 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 2,4,6-tribromophenol, 2,6-dibromo-4-chlorophenol, 8-hydroxyquinoline shows that there is an extra band around 3500 cm⁻¹ which has been attributed to Sn-OH bond in these compounds¹⁸. Rocking frequency due to free hydroxyl group has been found in the region close to 900 cm⁻¹. This band has, however, been found to be absent in case of picric acid when the spectrum was taken in nujol mull. This may be attributed to the bridging nature of hydroxy group in solid compound which becomes free in solution. However, no indication for the presence of hydroxyl group has been obtained from proton nuclear magnetic resonance perhaps due to fast exchange of hydroxyl protons.

TABLE 3—FAR INFRA-RED SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS OF CATEGORY A

Compounds of Bu ₂ SnO with \rightarrow	phenol (1:1)	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenol (1:1)	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenol (1:1)	β -Naphthol (1:1)	<i>p</i> -nitro phenol (1:1)	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenol (1:1)	<i>m</i> -Methyl phenol (1:1)	<i>o</i> -Methyl phenol (1:1)	<i>p</i> -Cyano phenol (1:1)	<i>p</i> -Amino phenol (1:1)	<i>m</i> -nitro phenol (1:1)
$\nu_{as}(\text{Sn-O-Sn})\text{cm}^{-1}$	585	610	620	625	625	630	610	600	600	605	630
$\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ and $\nu(\text{Sn-C})\text{cm}^{-1}$	565	575	535	575	595	540	560 b	565	550	580	600
	535	565	535	535	550 k	500			510	538	550
		550			513					518	
$\nu(\text{Sn-O-Sn})\text{cm}^{-1}$	425 w	450 w	460 w	463 w	450 w	450 w	450 w	—	445 m	455 w	450w
$\nu(\text{Sn-O-Sn})\text{cm}^{-1}$	400	420	410 k	430	395	410	410	420 b	390	410 k	400
		400 k	400 k	395						400 k	
$\nu(\text{Sn-O})\text{cm}^{-1}$	305	305	300	315	315	285	295	315	320	320	295
Unassigned bands	233	367	345	513	276	350 w	235-40	230	270	225	
		225	288	495	212	325 w			240		
		210	280	288		230 m			210		

b = broad, k = kink, m = medium, w = weak, s = strong. 225

TABLE 4—¹HNMR SPECTRAL DATA OF N-DIBUTYLTIN PHENOXIDES AND ANISOLES

	In CCl ₄ (ring protons)	In DMSO—d ₆ (ring protons)	CH ₃	Dibutyl
Anisole phenol/ DBSnO (1 : 1)	566cps (meta, H's) 541cps (O, pH's) 560cps (4H's) 519cps (6H's)	586cps 560cps 578cps 545cps		105 (m) (36H's)
<i>o</i> -Chloro- anisole <i>o</i> -Chloro- phenol/ DBSnO (1 : 1)	572cps 540cps 547cps (m) (8H's)	586cps 558cps 561cps		100cps (m) (36H's)
<i>p</i> -Chloro- anisole <i>p</i> -Chloro- phenol/ DBSnO (1 : 1)	564cps 526cps 558cps (4H's) 511cps (4H's)			100cps (m) (36H's)
β -Naphthyl methyl- ether	602 586 574 560 552			
β -Naphthol DBSnO(1:1)	601 589 570 543 539	(14H's)		110cps (m) (36H's)
<i>p</i> -Nitro- anisole	640cps 550cps			
<i>p</i> -Nitro- phenol DB SnO (1 : 1)	656cps (4H's) 531cps (4H's)			110cps (m) (36H's)
<i>m</i> -Nitro- anisole	590cps (m)			
<i>m</i> -Nitro- phenol/ DBSnO (1 : 1) in CDCl ₃	575cps (m) (8H's)			120cps (m) (36H's)
<i>o</i> -Methyl- anisole	544cps (m)			
<i>o</i> -Cresol/ DBSnO (1 : 1)	537 (8H's) cps		172cps 176cps (6H's)	100cps (m) (36H's)
<i>m</i> -Methyl- anisole	539 (m) cps		173cps	
<i>m</i> -Cresol/ DBSnO (1 : 1)	521cps (8H's)		178cps (6H's)	105cps (m) (36H's)
<i>p</i> -Methyl- anisole	537cps		172cps	
<i>p</i> -Methyl- phenyl/ DBSnO(1:1) (8H's)	522cps		178cps (6H's)	100cps (36H's)
<i>p</i> -Cyano- phenol (in CDCl ₃)	577cps 528cps			
<i>p</i> -Cyano- phenol/ DBSnO(1:1)	598cps (4H's) 526cps (4H's)			115cps (36H's)

TABLE 4 (Contd)

In CC_4 (ring protons)	In $DMSO-d_6$ (ring protons)	CH_3	Dibutyl
2, 4, 6-Tri- 607cps bromo- phenylmethylether			
2, 4, 6-Tri- 592cps bromophenol/ DBSnO(1:1) (2H's)			120cps (18H's)
2,6-Dibromo-602cps 4-chloro- phenylmethyl- ether			
2,6-Dibromo-586cps 4-chloro- phenol/ DBSnO(1:1) (H2's)			120cps (18H's)
2,4,6-Trini- — trophenol/ DBSnO(1 : 1)			120cps
8-Hydroxy- 692cps (1H) quinoline (1 : 1) 636cps (1Hs) 575cps (4H's)			
8-Hydroxy- quinoline/ 670cps (1H's) DBSnO(1:1) 632cps (1H's) 590cps (1H's)			
566cps 560cps 547cps(d) } (3H's)			105cps (18H's)
8-Hydroxy- quinoline/ 666cps (2H's) DBSnO(2:1) 629cps (2H's) 586cps (2H's) 553cps (6H's)			100cps (18H's)

TABLE 5—INFRA-RED SPECTRAL DATA FOR THE COMPOUNDS OF CATEGORY B AND C

Compounds of DBSnO(Dibutyl- tin oxide) with :->	Picric Acid + DBSnO (1 : 1) in $CHCl_3$	2, 4, 6- Tribromo- phenol (1 : 1) in CCl_4	2, 6-dibromo-4- chlorophenol (1 : 1) in CCl_4	8-Hydroxy- quinoline (1 : 1) in $CHCl_3$	8-Hydroxy- quinoline (2 : 1) in $CHCl_3$	<i>o</i> -hydroxy pyridine (2 : 1) in nujol
$\nu(Sn-O-Sn)$	868 (in Nujol)					825
$\nu(C-H)$	2920	2850	2850 k 2900	2820	2900	—
$\nu(OH)$	3470	3500	3490	3250b	—	—
$\delta(OH)$	910	910	915	915		
$\nu(C=N)$				1700 s (1680 w)a		1670 (1600)b (1650)c
$\nu(O-Sn-O)$					655	660

(a) For 8-hydroxyquinoline, (b) for sodium salt of *o*-Hydroxypyridine (23)
(c) for *o*-Hydroxy pyridine (23).

TABLE 6—FAR I.R. FOR THE COMPOUNDS OF CATEGORY B AND C.

Compound of Bu_2SnO with :->	Picric acid (1 : 1)	2, 4, 6-Tribromo-phenol (1 : 1)	2, 6-Dibromo-4-chloro-phenol (1 : 1)	8-Hydroxy-quinoline (1 : 1)	8-Hydroxy-quinoline (1 : 2)	2-Hydroxy-pyridine (1 : 2)
$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O-Sn-O})\text{cm}^{-1}$	605	585	600	615 600	620	620
$\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ and $\nu(\text{Sn-C})\text{cm}^{-1}$	518	565 520	565 525	570 515	580 520 450	570 530 450
$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O-Sn-O})\text{cm}^{-1}$	444 w	450 w	430 w	430	437	435
$\nu(\text{Sn}\leftarrow\text{O})\text{cm}^{-1}$	280	315	300	310	275	315
$\nu(\text{Sn}\leftarrow\text{N})\text{cm}^{-1}$				415 b	425	400

Other features are very much similar to the compounds discussed in category A.

Category C

It contains 1 : 2 compounds of dibutyltin oxide with 8-hydroxyquinoline and 2-hydroxy pyridine. The quinoline compound is monomeric with the two butyl groups cis to each other. The formation of 2 : 1 complexation is indicated by the presence of bands at 655, 450, 437 cm^{-1} (Tables 5 and 6) for asymmetric and symmetric stretches of (O-Sn-O) bond. A strong absorption at 400 cm^{-1} has been attributed to Sn-N bonds^{21, 22}.

Band due to quinolinolato part in the ¹HNMR spectrum of the compound is more complex than that of the ligand itself. Had the two butyl groups been trans to each other the pattern of quinolinolato ring protons would not have changed at all as compared to that for 8-hydroxyquinoline. This suggests cis stereochemistry for this compound which has also been supported by Mossbauer spectrum^{19, 20}.

The 2 : 1 complex of 2-hydroxypyridine with Bu_2SnO is a white solid. Due to insoluble nature of the complex, nmr and molecular weight could not be taken. However, molecular weight found by Rast method in camphor shows the complex to be monomer. The ligand and the complex have almost similar spectra except that the bands in 3100-3400 cm^{-1} range are absent in case of the complex. It suggests that pyridone form has almost vanished²³. The band at 660 cm^{-1} has been ascribed to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O-Sn-O})$ while the weak bands at 450 and 435 cm^{-1} have been attributed to $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O-Sn-O})$ ²⁰. The coordination of nitrogen to metal is indicated by the presence of bands at 420 and 385 cm^{-1} ,^{21, 22}.

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